

Title:

Efficiency Enhancement of Part Manufacturing by Virtual Machining Systems

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Abstract: With the aid of computers, simulating and modeling of a physical manufacturing system become possible in virtual environments [1]. As a result, optimization methods can be applied to the simulated manufacturing process in the virtual environments to improve efficiency of parts production.

Keywords: Virtual Machining, Efficiency of Part Production

1- Introduction

Virtual manufacturing systems are developed by simulating real manufacturing processes in digital environments in order to increase accuracy as well as efficiency of part production [4]. To increase efficiency of part production, optimized parameters of manufacturing process can be calculated by applying optimization methods to the simulated manufacturing processes in virtual environments. As a result, more added value in part manufacturing can be achieved by analyzing and optimizing effective parameters of simulated manufacturing processes in virtual environments.

2- Applications

- To increase efficiency of parts production, optimization techniques can be applied to the simulated machining process [2].
- To increase accuracy as well as efficiency of part manufacturing, errors of actual machined parts can be simulated and analyzed in virtual environments [3].

References

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